

"THE ROLE OF THEORETICAL LEXICOGRAPHY IN LANGUAGE
EVOLUTION"

Kamola Alautdinova,

Senior teacher, PhD of the TIIAME., National
Research University ,

E-mail: kamola.mansurovna.phd@gmail.com

Phone: (93) 3753355

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14205225>

Abstract. This paper provides a comprehensive overview of theoretical lexicography, highlighting its definition, purpose, and significance in the field of linguistics. It discusses the relationship between lexicography and linguistics, emphasizing how linguistic theories inform dictionary-making. The work explores the contributions of key researchers, such as Zgusta and Wiegand, to the development of heuristic tools.

Keywords. Theoretical Lexicography, Dictionary Development, Lexicographic Model, Informative Functions, Communicative Functions, Normative Functions

Аннотация. В этой статье представлен всесторонний обзор теоретической лексикографии, подчеркивающий ее определение, цель и значение в области лингвистики. В ней обсуждается связь между лексикографией и лингвистикой, подчеркивая, как лингвистические теории информируют о создании словарей. В работе исследуется вклад ключевых исследователей, таких как Згуста и Виганд, в разработку эвристических инструментов.

Ключевые слова. Теоретическая лексикография, Развитие словаря, Лексикографическая модель, Информативные функции, Коммуникативные функции, Нормативные функции.

Introduction. Theoretical lexicography is a vital branch of linguistics dedicated to the study and development of dictionaries and lexical resources. It encompasses the principles guiding the creation, organization, and evaluation of dictionaries, ensuring they meet the evolving needs of language users. As language continues to develop, the role of theoretical lexicography becomes increasingly important in facilitating effective communication and preserving linguistic accuracy.

It is particularly noteworthy that one of the requirements of today's development is the formation of professional knowledge among university graduates and the ability to apply the concepts specific to their fields correctly. Thus, knowing English for specific professions means knowing the relevant field's terminology. Indeed, terminology forms the basis of professional communication, constituting its core. Furthermore, to successfully carry out professional activities, future specialists must not only know a foreign language but also participate in professional communication

processes in that language. The theoretical lexicography requires a critical study of its functions and structure through the application of "heuristic tools." Zgusta and Wiegand have contributed some of these heuristic tools to the application of theoretical lexicography [4].

Additionally, Zgusta, who laid the foundation for lexicography as a research field and integrated it into the linguistic disciplines, is recognized as one of the scholars regarded as the father of modern lexicography for his contributions to science. According to Zgusta, "a lexicographer needs to have a deep understanding of the field of linguistics and be familiar with related research [4]."

Later, the connection between lexicography and linguistics was practically studied. In the 1980s and 1990s, among the research conducted in the area of metalexicography (also known as theoretical lexicography), Herbert Wiegand's theory, which created the theoretical foundations of lexicography, gained prominence. According to G.E. Wiegand, while linguistics influences lexicography, the object of lexicography is not language but dictionaries. Therefore, Wiegand focused his research not only on the composition and naming of dictionaries but also on their structure. His research concluded with the publication of an international encyclopedia of lexicography, dedicated to several pressing issues of lexicography, including the popularity of dictionaries, types of dictionaries, the history and theory of lexicography, and the structural components and constructions of dictionaries [4].

It should be noted that the lexicography theory created by F. Hausmann and G. Wiegand is recognized by the scientific community as a modern, comprehensive, and extensive model. Indeed, the theory established by F. Hausmann and G. Wiegand is based on the premise that the structure created for each conveyed information can be modified by the lexicographer for its intended purpose. The theory applied by F. Hausmann and G. Wiegand relates to the gathering of relevant information for dictionaries according to lexicographic tasks, as well as ensuring the presentation of both existing and newly created information that is significant for the user [3].

It is well known that dictionaries play an important role in a person's spiritual and cultural life, as they reflect the knowledge and experience accumulated by humanity. Additionally, dictionaries perform informative, communicative, and normative functions. Their informative function introduces individuals to accumulated knowledge and experiences, while the communicative function provides readers with information about their native language and foreign languages. The

normative function records the meanings and usages of existing lexemes in the language, helping to improve them [1].

Thus, the stability of a specific terminological system is primarily determined by its organization and the correspondence between expression and content. A terminological system that meets these requirements can overcome scientific disciplines and enter the modern metalanguage of a specific science.

It is appropriate to recognize the significance of logistics terminology as it represents one of the most important areas of human activity with social relevance. Logistics-related terms are generally divided into common and specific terms. Common terms express universal concepts that are used across multiple fields. In particular, the specific terms of the logistics field belong exclusively to that field, thus occupying a place in the logistics lexicon. The large number of such terms is distinguished by the activity of the "transport" semantic field and its high differentiability. Logistics terms have a special history of study, and in world linguistics, especially in German and English linguistics, the transport terminological system is quite well organized.

For this reason, it is important to take into account the opinions of certain scholars when creating specialized terminological dictionaries, as they serve as significant factors in their formation. In particular, V.D. Devkin's dictionaries not only provide information but also shape the lexicon. O.S. Akhmanova emphasizes the need to consider specific aspects of dictionary creation, word choice (thesaurus), and content (encyclopedic) elements, while V.G. Gak points out that the following tasks are crucial for creating explanatory and translation dictionaries: 1) the mutual consistency of synchrony and diachrony, 2) adherence to the demands of language and speech, and 3) the relationship between linguistic and extralinguistic information. These considerations ensure that any dictionary is complete, meets contemporary demands, and is ideologically stable [1].

Conclusion. Theoretical lexicography plays an essential role in the ongoing evolution of language and communication. By examining the principles underlying dictionary creation and organization, researchers can enhance the quality and effectiveness of lexical resources. One of the most intriguing aspects of theoretical lexicography is its ability to adapt to the dynamic nature of language. As new words and phrases emerge in response to cultural, technological, and social changes, lexicographers must be agile, constantly updating and revising dictionaries to reflect

contemporary usage. This adaptability not only preserves language but also serves to document the evolution of thought and society.

Reference list:

1. **Гринев С.В.** Введение в терминоведение. – М.: Московский Лицей, 1993. – С.9
2. **Taurai Imbayarwo.** A biblical Hebrew lexicon for translators based on Recent developments in theoretical lexicography Dissertation presented for the Degree of Doctor of Literature at the University of Stellenbosch.:Stellenbosch University, 2008. – 238 p.
3. **Zgusta, L.** 2006. Lexicography Then and Now. Tübingen: Max Niemeyer Verlag (Lexicographica Series Maior 129).; Wiegand, H. E. and Kucera 1982. Brockhaus-Wahrig: Deutsches Wörterbuch auf dem Prüfstand der praktischen Lexikologie. II. Part: 1st vol. (A-BT), 2nd vol. (BUFZ), 3rd vol. (G-JZ). in: Wiegand, H E (ed.), Studien zur neuhochdeutschen Lexikographie II. Hildesheim/New York: Germanistische Linguistik 3-6/80.
4. **Zgusta L.** Manual of lexicography. The Hague: Mouton. – Praha, Academia, 1971. – P.39.
5. **Gouws R. H. and D. J. Prinsloo.** Principles and Practice of South African Lexicography. Stellenbosch: – Sun Press. 2005. – P.2